

Compare and contrast the process of primary and secondary succession.

Ecological succession is how environments change over time and is necessary in the reforesting and reaccumulating of biomass in the world. Succession is not affected by seasonal variations and typical disturbances, but rather, responds to disturbances from outside sources like humans and global warming (Holden, 2018). Understanding succession is valuable, as the world continues to change at a more rapid pace and succession will become necessary in many areas. Succession is significant because it is the only option for continued existence of an ecosystem even after its resilience has failed. Primary and secondary succession are the two main types of ecological succession and should be defined, compared, and contrasted to thoroughly comprehend their respective natures.

Primary succession “starts in areas that are completely devoid of life such as after a volcano eruption or glacier retreat. There is no soil” (Holden, 2018, pg.286). Despite the lack of soil, organisms bordering these lifeless areas pioneer their way onto devoid surfaces and colonise the area with life. Secondary succession, on the other hand, not only takes place much quicker, but also doesn't require pioneer species. This is due to secondary succession which takes place “after less dramatic disturbances, such as after a forest fire or the abandonment of agricultural fields. After these events soil is present, though probably degraded” (Holden, 2018, pg.286). Secondary succession occurs faster due to the preexisting soil and seeds embedded in it, only growth is necessary rather than colonisation followed by growth. The main differences between succession types are the existence or lack of soil, and the rate at which they occur, though the species in the case of secondary succession leads to further differences.

The species which are seen in the two types of succession are vastly different. Both occur through many successional stages from pioneer to early, followed by mid and late, eventually reaching a climax community, a state of equilibrium in an ecosystem. The pioneer community for primary succession is “made up of lichens and mosses and other autotrophic species which do not require soil, but can cling to the rock” (Holden, 2018, pg.288), a necessary trait for species colonising the rocky face of a volcanic eruption for example. In secondary succession, the pioneer species, first to grow back after a fire for instance, already exist in the soil, and with the recent clearing of disruptions to sunlight and water, such as larger trees, they are able to grow at much faster rates. There are some species in fact like Cistaceae, who have adapted to their dry and fire-prone ecosystems like the Mediterranean, whose seeds will lay dormant on the ground and will be unable to germinate until a fire reduces the competition to ash (Luna *et.al.*, 2023). Additionally, the relationship between vegetation and soils, through succession, will change to favour more generalist species. One plant which is one of their first to be seen in primary succession is the Sitka alder (*Alnus sinuata*), which grows in the primitive soils; poor in water retention, structure, and nitrogen (Cox and Moore, 2005). Cox and Moore (2005) continue that this nitrogen fixating plant then creates

a more microbe and nitrogen rich environment, fertilising the soil and making the conditions perfect for other, less adapted vegetation, which inevitably shade out and kill off any remaining Sitka alder. Most pioneer species are r-selected species meaning they are most common in unstable environments, reproduce very few times but with lots of offspring, mature early, and live shorter lives in comparison to their K-selected alternatives (Cox and Moore, 2005). Due to this, both primary and secondary succession processes will see an abundance of species, many of which are K-selected, seen in climax communities. Though in the same amount of time, primary succession will take longer to reach a climax community and spend more time with r-selected pioneer species than secondary succession.

In a climax community biodiversity, or species richness and evenness, is also at a climax, with increased abundance and diversity of species. Species evenness exhibits very little change from the first year of growth in secondary succession, all the way up to the fifteenth year of growth, however, from year fifteen to twenty-five, species diversity nearly doubles, and certainly does so by forty years (Cox and Moore, 2005). In Cox and Moore's (2005, pgs.66-67) specific example from an old field exhibiting secondary succession in Illinois, it is possible to note the increase in species diversity as well as richness, and as this growth towards a climax community is universal in succession, it displays a similarity between the two types. Despite this example of an ideal climax community, it is still possible for one species to remain dominant in a climax community environment, thereby reducing the diversity but not affecting the biomass of the ecosystem (Cox and Moore, 2005). Both primary and secondary succession will lead to a climax community in the most optimal outcome, though with varying levels of species richness and evenness, effecting the biodiversity of the ecosystem.

Biodiversity is important to the resilience of an environment, however once resilience is disrupted by humans, global warming, or natural causes, like fires or volcanic eruptions, succession will follow. Primary succession is defined by its lack of soil, abundance of pioneer species and slower growth period, whereas secondary succession keeps its soil, and due to this requires fewer pioneer species and displays faster growth. Both types of succession, however, have r-selected species which sacrifice themselves to improve conditions for more generalist and K-selected species to create the ideal climax community, which is diverse and shows more resilience in the face of change.

Bibliography

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